

Strengths and Weaknesses of the Ministry of Information and Culture of Afghanistan in Managing Private T.V Stations (From 2010 to 2020)

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To get how to manage private media (television) in Afghanistan, Kabul. Afghanistan.

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Abstract.

In this study, the strengths and weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in management of Private T.V Stations were investigated. To achieve this goal, in addition to asking research questions, the concepts, topics discussed in media management and media theories were studied and then descriptive type and mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative) were used. The sample population received a satisfactory answer to the research question by distributing a questionnaire and conducting interviews with experts from Afghan Journalists Union, TV staff and Ministry of Information and Culture of Afghanistan. The results of this study showed that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan was not very successful in managing Private T.V Stations. The strengths of this ministry in terms of media management were: issuing licenses to televisions, formulating broadcasting policies, passing the media law, providing a suitable platform for the activities of private T.V Stations, and in some cases managing televisions privately. However, the weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of Private T.V Stations were: lack of rule of law, breaking the law by the ministry itself and etc. Therefore, media management by the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan can make the performance of mass media activities more effective.

Keywords: Media Management; Management on Media; Management in Media; Press Freedom; Afghanistan

Introduction

Today, mass media is the main source of information and reflection of thoughts and ideas, that can have a significant impact on the psyche, thoughts and ideas and even the beliefs of the people and in showing crises and showing solutions by playing an important role (Mehraj atl, 2014). On the other hand, just as televisions play an important role in raising the level of awareness, culture and knowledge of the people in society, on the contrary, these same televisions have great problems in shaping public opinion in a negative direction. Which will have dire consequences for the traditional and illiterate society of Afghanistan, also play a significant role (Amedie, 2015). The effects of private T.V Stations activities can be assessed in two parts; One includes the positive effects of private T.V Stations and the other is the negative effects on the minds and public opinion of the people and society (Ritchie, 2013). One of the benefits of free TVs is that TVs are more effective for the society and the people, providing accurate information about the events and happenings that take place in our environment, because most people expect this from the media. To inform them about the current events and serious events of the country and the world (Westoff, atl. 2011). But some also consider the reasons for the activities and negative effects of televisions to be the privacy of these media, which means that the televisions in our country are private and free and are supported by certain individuals and certain groups. In such televisions, the role of government and government management is not very effective (Mishra, 2010). Another reason that a private

T.V Stations can somehow have a negative impact on people's minds is the lack of serious attention and careful control of the quality or message of a film, series or program by the relevant government institutions. Over the years, we have seen that a number of media outlets that broadcast their programs for our people and society are mostly derived from western and foreign cultures, which has led to cultural invasion in the country and it has left negative effects on our society (Thomas, 2009). Another important reason for the negative effects can be the lack of a clear policy and the lack of a comprehensive method of care in the management of mass media by the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan (Levinson, 2016).

Because the media is considered the fourth pillar of society in popular systems, it needs serious control and care, especially in the age of information explosion and the age when the world has become a small village (Walsh-Childers, 2018). The media, especially television, has the largest audience and viewership, and directly and indirectly affects the public mind (Westoff, 2011). Televisions need very regular and correct management because the management of televisions is like public management, with the difference that its materials are cultural products and its audience is the general public. Media managers, in addition to the responsibility of administrators and providing benefits and motivating them, decision-making, planning and launching various projects based on the requirements of the country, should be able to use technology to bring cultural products to the national and transnational level. Produce (Wyman, 2012). The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has played an important role in strengthening freedom of expression, the growth of free television, and the issuance of licenses in accordance with various policies and programs, and the presence of multiple television shows this, which the homogeneous masses of people desire. They show that all this was due to the management of the televisions by this ministry.

On the other hand, the activity of the media is a necessity in a society, but what should be expected from the visual media is not seen from our media in our country. The content of the programs of these media is often lower level and no attention is paid to the quality of the programs at all (Rimscha, 2020). Media congestion and unplanned media on the one hand and violations and actions against the law and national values on the other hand, has caused that instead of the growth of desirable mentalities in the country, mentalities are distorted by the media. The general themes of the country's visual media are: "foreign music, serials and films, and Indian and western songs," which is one of the general problems in eradicating Afghan culture and instead promoting foreign culture through this medium. In this regard, it can be said that this point indicates the weak management of the government and the government does not allow itself to intervene in order to use its authority and responsibility to prevent it from violating the law and exceeding the limits of freedoms. So knowing why the government does not want to intervene and manage so that on the one hand the freedom of expression and media freedoms that will cause a cultural crisis in society is not used, and on the other hand, the negative use in shaping public opinion in favour, It is very important and necessary that the media does not take place.

According to the subject of the research, the purpose of this research is the most important weaknesses of ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan in the management of the country's televisions in terms of law violations and media violations and its sub-objectives; Expressing the most important strengths of ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of televisions, recognizing how the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan manages the management of televisions and its intervention powers, identifying the factors affecting the weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in managing private televisions, receiving appropriate solutions for the management of private

T.V Stations by the ministry of Information and culture of Afghanistan. To achieve these goals, the questions that can be asked are what are the most important strengths and weaknesses of ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's private T.V Stations? What method has the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan taken in managing the media, especially private T.V Stations? What are the important achievements of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's televisions in recent years? What are the effective management factors on the weakness of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in managing private T.V Stations? What are the existing solutions to strengthen the weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan in managing the media, especially Private T.V Stations? Since this research is new in Afghanistan, and the necessary information in the field of media management in the country is not available, therefore, the researcher in this study does not use the hypothesis and directly answers the research questions.

Research literature

According to the Afghan constitution, freedom and human dignity are inviolable. The state is obliged to respect and protect human freedom and dignity "(Constitution, 2003, Article 24. p. 79; Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1327, Articles 3 and 4. p. 3; Ahmadzai, 1392, p. 24; Max Guideline Planck, 2007, p. 151). According to Dr. Kazem Motamednejad (2000), freedom of the press in the general sense means that "freedom of the press in general, the free search, collection and acquisition of news and information and public opinion, their free transmission, the free publication of newspapers, the free distribution of programs radio and television include the free reception and study of the press and the free reception of the mentioned programs" (Motamednejad, 2000, p. 25; Mishra, 2010). Thus, the main classification of communication theories is summarized in the four press theories of American scientists, in the light of which the other scientists of the world classified the press systems according to the prevailing policies of the time. The authoritarian theory of the truth system was not seen as the achievement of the masses; rather, it was seen as the achievement of a number of prominent religious figures who appeared to be in the guiding position of their followers (Siebert, Peterson, & Schramm, 1963; Avshalom, 2013; Igor, Klyukanov, Sinekopova, 2014). The truth was in the hands of the powerful at the time, and the press was applied vertically from top to bottom (Mokshatit, 2011). Liberal theory was proposed by scientists such as John Milton, the British revolutionary poet, and the philosopher John Locke. According to this theory, man was not known as a dependent being, who was always guided and led; rather, he was known more as a rational being, who can decide for himself when dealing with issues and truth, good and bad, happiness and sorrow, and no theory or will is imposed on him (Motamednejad, 2007; Esmat Elahi, 1382; Küng, 2007). In the theory of social responsibility, the role and social function of the media has received special attention. In fact, based on this media system, in addition to having freedom, they also have important social responsibilities (Mostafavi, 1389, p. 16; Adibe, 2017). Communist theory is rooted in Marxist determinism and is based on the urgent need to maintain the political dominance of a party. In this theory, the press is state-owned, unlike the old model of authoritarianism, which was based on private property. In this new model, the motivation for profit-seeking has disappeared and the concept of positive freedom has replaced the concept of negative freedom (Motamednejad, 2007, p. 229; Costello, 2018).

Media management is the process of optimal use of all capabilities and capacities, including physical, technological, artistic and human, in order to produce, reproduce and distribute purposeful messages within the accepted value system, with the ultimate goal of having a favourable effect on the audience takes place (Manib, 2012, p. 8; Costello, 2018). The media

industry experienced fundamental changes through new technologies, which completely changed the structure of the industry. Media institutions took on new forms of investment, economic and managerial work in the form of a new industry. Today, media companies are growing and transforming, and media owners can no longer manage the media. Therefore, in order for the media to become professional, they managed the media, scientifically, as a new field (Jahanshahi, 2011; Farhang va Arbatai, 2004; Albarran, 2014). There are three types of media in terms of ownership, type of administration and the status of the ruling system: state media; mass media; and private media. State-owned media are media outlets that pay all royalties and revenues to the government, which is programmed according to government policy. National or public media are media in addition to earning their points and income through the government, receiving their expenses from the public payment document and the people's participation fee, and the government is under the control of the government. Private and commercial media are media outlets that are responsible for their actions in accordance with the general rules and regulations of the press and the observance of professional ethics and national and international press barriers, and this group of media through commercials, commercial support and the sale of products are funded, and their legal status is governed by commercial regulations and trade laws.

The ownership of the first group of media belongs to the government, the second group of media belongs to the people, and the third group of media belongs to private individuals or legal entities. Each of these properties has an impact on the way it is run, the extent to which it responds and its quality to the people, and the manner in which managers are appointed or selected, the framework governing rules and regulations, the monitoring method, and the like. Are. Although the first and second types of property are considered public property, or in other words belong to the "treasury", the degree of public intervention and oversight varies how they are managed, and media management, especially its policy aspects, is directly related to this. The methods are related (Jan, 1388; Munib, 1392; Mohseni, 1381; Adibe, 2017). According to various scientists, television has had an impact on daily life more than any other technical innovation outside the realm of lucrative employment. For example, people who own a car spend on average only six percent more time traveling than people who do not, and when they do housework, when they own a home appliance such as a refrigerator, washing machine and dryer. Usually do not change (Giddens, 2008; Albarran, 2014).

Table 1: Comparison of four theories of media control (Motamednejad, 2007, p. 230)

Characteristics	Soviet Communist Theory	Theory of social responsibility	Liberal theory	Authoritarian theory
Genesis and expansion period	In the Soviet Union after the 1917 Communist Revolution	20th Century in the USA	The period after the victory of the British Constitutional Revolution in 1688-9, the victory of the American Independence Wars (1776) and the French Revolution (1789)	16th and 17th centuries in England, then in other European countries and in the contemporary period in some other countries of the world
Philosophical origin	Marxist, Leninist, Stalinist ideas, with mixtures of Hegel and Russian thinkers	Decisions and Reports of the 1945 Press Freedom Commission, University of Chicago, Journalists' Perspectives, and Principles of	By John Milton, John Locke, and John Stuart Mill, and the General Philosophy of Natural Law Rationalism	The philosophy of the authoritarian power of the king, the government or both

		Professional Journalistic Ethics		
The main objective	Contributing to the success and cure of the Soviet socialist system and especially the party dictatorship	Awareness, entertainment and sales, especially participation in social disputes and debates	Awareness, entertainment and sales and in particular help to discover the truth of government oversight	Support and promote government policies and service to the government
Who has the right to use the media?	Loyal and trusted members of the party	Anyone who has something to say	Anyone who has the necessary financial resources	Those who have special permission from the king or have obtained a similar license.
How to control the media?	Supervision and economic and political action of the government	Community, public opinion, consumer actions and professional ethics	Through the process of the individual's right to seek the truth of the free market of ideas and exchanges	Government and industry licenses, special permits and censorship
Prohibitions	How to control the media	Serious invasion of privacy and vital interests of society	Defamation, disregard for public morals and decency, military disobedience and riot in time	Use of political apparatus and authorities
Ownership	Public	Private, unless the government takes over to provide public service.	More private	Private and Public
Their main differences with each other	They are state-owned and formally controlled as a government weapon.	The media must take on the responsibility of social responsibility, otherwise others must determine how they act.	Tools for monitoring government and meeting other needs of society	A tool for enforcing government policies, even if owned by the media.

Methods and materials

In this research, descriptive method and mixed research method has been used to obtain more accurate information and analyse them. This method includes quantitative and qualitative research methods. In this research, the method of reviewing valid documents has been used to supplement this dissertation in the preface section and review of past works. In this research, according to the subject and purpose of the research and obtaining reliable and accurate results, three tools have been used to collect information and information, such as questionnaires, interviews and review of documents. It should be said that using these three tools to collect information for the desired answers and questions in accordance with the goal can be obtained without problems.

A. Questionnaire: Open and closed questions have been used in the questionnaires according to the subject and purpose of the research. Out of a total of 119 questionnaires, 29 were distributed to the TV executives representing a television station, and I retrieved 23 questionnaires. The remaining 90 questionnaires were distributed to members of the Journalists' Unions for 3 unions, of which 13 questionnaires were distributed to the Afghan Women Journalists Association, 22 questionnaires to the Free Journalists' Association and 55 questionnaires to the National Journalists' Union. We brought. It is noteworthy that the

questionnaires were distributed to journalists in the form of random sampling. Sample questionnaires can be found in the appendices (1 and 2). B. Interview: In this research, interview questions were asked to get answers to the research questions. A total of 8 interviews were conducted in person, of which 6 were media experts and the other 2 were officials of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan. C. Document review: This method has been used in order to achieve research goals and find a good management model according to the ruling system, which is used to make research scientific and fruitful from scientific books, journals, journals, journals and other scientific works. Used.

In this study, in order to gather more information and information about all the free televisions in Kabul that have national broadcasts, their responsible managers who represent a television included the participants of this research. Because each TV station had more than 170 employees and due to lack of cooperation in this field, financial resources and time constraints, we could not distribute questionnaires to all TV members. Also, the TV staffs were not aware of how the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan was managed. On the other hand, in order to get the desired answers, the journalism of journalistic unions is included in our research, in which a total of 9 journalistic unions were active in Afghanistan, out of which 9 unions from three unions using random sampling method, sample Among these three unions, a questionnaire was distributed to 5% of their members using random sampling method. The unions each consisted of 1,100 members of the National Journalists' Union, 5% of whom numbered 55, of whom 37 were in Kabul and 18 in the provinces. The Free Journalists Association, which had 450 members, had 5% of its members, 22 of whom were 16 in Kabul and 8 in the provinces, and the Afghan women Journalists' Association, which had 250 members, of which 5% had 13 members. Fortunately, all its members were present in Kabul using a random sampling method.

Also, among the top 21 experts and media experts, interviews were conducted using random sampling method and 6 of them were interviewed.

Quantitative findings

Raw data, findings and figures were analysed using SPSS statistical software and after analysing the findings, the results were provided to users in the form of information. According to the research findings, 5 managers, who constituted 21.7% of this sample, have spent 2-3 years of their television activity. As many as 5 executives, who made up 21.7% of the sample, have had their TVs broadcast for between 4-5 years. Of the 4 managers, who made up 17.4% of the sample, their TVs were in operation for 5-6 years, and of the 9 managers, who made up 39.1% of this sample, had their TVs in operation for more than 7 years Their activity is over. Therefore, it can be said that most of the free televisions in Kabul have been operating for more than 7 years. Findings show that 19 managers, who made up 82.6 of this sample population, had between 120 and 150 employees. Two of the executives, who made up 8.7 percent of the sample, had between 150 and 300 employees, and the other two executives, who made up 8.7 percent of the sample, had more than 300 employees. Also, 13 people, who made up 14.4% of the sample of union members, were respondents of the Women's Association of Journalists. A total of 55 people, who made up 61.1% of the sample union, were members of the National Union of Journalists, and 23, who made up 24.4% of the sample, were members of the Free Journalists' Association.

Description of the main variables

To answer the question, are you satisfied with the freedom of the media among the respondents of the responsible managers of the televisions? They chose a very satisfied answer. Nine

people, who made up 39.1% of the participants, chose the satisfied answer. Five people, representing 21.7% of the respondents, chose the moderately satisfied answer. One person, who made up 4.3%, chose the least satisfied answer and the other one, who made up 4.3% of the sample, chose the very least satisfied answer. Therefore, it can be concluded that most TV executives are satisfied with the freedom of the media. But among the 9 union respondents, who made up 10% of the sample, are you satisfied with the freedom of the media? Very satisfied with the answer; 35 people, 38.9% of whom made this sample, satisfied answer; 25 people, who made up 27.8% of the sample, had a moderately satisfied response; Thirteen people, who made up 14.4% of the sample, chose the unsatisfactory answer and 8, who made up 8.9% of the sample, chose the very unsatisfied answer. It can be inferred from the results that most of the respondents in this sample were very satisfied with the freedom of the media.

The results show that, among the respondents, the responsible managers of the televisions, how much management do you think the free media (televisions) needed for the question? Too many answers; 4 people, who made up 17.4% of this figure, answered a lot; 4 people, who constituted 17.4% of this sample, chose moderate response and the other 2 people, who constituted 8.7% of this sample, chose low response. From the results obtained, it can be inferred that most of the respondents of the responsible managers of the televisions believed that the free media needed to be managed as much as the free televisions. But among the union members, how much do you think the free media (televisions) needed to answer this question? To 38, who made up 43.2% of this sample, the answer is too much; 28 tons, which accounted for 31.8% of this sample, high response; 17 tons; who made up 19.3% of this sample, the average response; 2 people who made up 2.3% of the sample had a low response and 3 people who made up 3.3% of the union sample chose a very low answer. Therefore, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of the union members commented that free media, especially free television, needed a lot of management.

Among the respondents of the responsible managers of televisions, to ask how much do you think that the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan manages the country's free televisions? To 2 people, who made up 8.7% of the sample, the answer is very high; the other 2, who made up 8.7% of the sample, had a high response; 7 tons, which accounted for 30.4% of the sample, average response; 6 people, who made up 26.1%, had a low response and the other 6 people, who made up 26.1% of this sample, chose a very low response. Therefore, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of the responsible managers of the televisions have commented that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan was moderately operated by free televisions. Also, among the respondents of the unions, the answer to this question was very high for 2 people, who constituted 2.3% of the sample members of the unions; 6 tons, which made up 6.7% of the sample, high response; 26 people, who made up 28.9% of the sample, average response; 19 people, who made up 21.6%, had a low response and 35 people, who made up 39.8% of the sample, chose a very low answer. In the end, the results show that most of the respondents, members of the union, commented that The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan manages very little free television.

Table 2: Publication policy of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan for free media from the perspective of responsible TV managers

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Confidence	Yes	10	43.5	43.5	43.5
	No	12	52.2	52.2	95.7
	I Don't know	1	4.3	4.3	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows that 10 people, who made up 43.5% of the sample of TV executives, have publications for free media (TVs) to ask the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan Policy? They had chosen the answer yes. Twelve people, who made up 52.2% of the sample of managers, chose the no answer and the other one, who made up 4.3% of the sample, chose the answer I do not know. Therefore, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of the responsible managers have commented that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has not yet developed a publishing policy for free media, especially free television. But among union members, 28, who made up 31.1% of the union sample, chose yes. A total of 47 people, who made up 32.2% of the sample of union members, chose the No answer, and another 15, who made up 16.7% of the union sample, chose the No Answer. From the results obtained, it can be inferred that most of the respondents of the union members had commented that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has not yet been able to formulate a publishing policy for free media, especially free television.

Table 3: Support of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan to free televisions from the perspective of responsible managers of televisions

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Confidence	Yes	8	34.8	34.8	34.8
	No	15	65.2	65.2	100.0
	Total	23	100.	100.0	

As shown in Table 3, among the respondents of the responsible managers of free televisions, to the question whether The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan supports televisions and their programs, there were 8 people, who constituted 34.8% of this research sample. , Chose the answer "yes" and 15 others, who made up 65.2% of the sample of televisions, chose the answer "no". From the results obtained, it can be concluded that most of the responsible managers of the televisions have commented that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan does not support free media, especially free televisions. But among the union members' respondents, 28, who made up 31.1% of the sample, chose the yes answer. 44, who made up 48.9% of the sample, chose the no answer. And 18 people, who made up 20% of the sample, chose the answer I do not know. Therefore, it can be concluded that most members of the unions believed that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan did not support free media, especially free television.

On the other hand, among the members of the Journalists' Union, the answer to this question was very high for 4 people, who made up 4.8% of this sample; 6 tons, which accounted for 7.1% of the sample, high response; 21 people, who made up 25% of this sample, average response; 21 people, who made up 25%, chose low response and another 32, who made up 38.1% of this sample, chose very low answer. Therefore, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of the union members have commented that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan supports and strengthens free television very little.

Table 4: Ministry of Information and Culture monitors free television from the perspective of responsible managers

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Confidence	Yes	10	43.5	43.5	43.5
	No	7	30.4	30.4	73.9
	I Don't know	6	26.1	26.1	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 4, 10 people, who made up 43% of this sample, chose yes. 7 people, who made up 30.4% of this sample, chose the no answer and 6 people, who made up 26.1% of this sample, chose the unknown answer. From the results obtained, it can be inferred that most of

the respondents of the responsible managers of the televisions believed that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan monitors the free televisions. Also, among the respondents, 39 members, who accounted for 43.3% of the sample, opted for the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan's oversight of free television. 34 people, who made up 37.8% of this sample, chose the I do not know answer, and 17 people, who made up 18.9% of this sample, chose the unknown answer. Therefore, it can be said that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan supervises free televisions. The results show that the response to 1 ton, which made up 4.8% of this sample, is very good; Another 1, which accounted for 4.8% of this sample, answered well; 8 tons, which accounted for 38.1% of this sample, average response; 5 people, who made up 23.8% of this sample, chose the bad answer and 6 people, who made up 28.6% of this sample, chose the very bad answer. The results can be interpreted as saying that most of the respondents of the responsible managers rated the supervision of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan on the programs of free television as average.

Table 5: shows the percentage of respondents to the questionnaire questions from both sample populations.

Table 5	Members of journalists' unions					Responsible managers				
	Very much	Much	Medium	Low	Very low	Very much	Much	Medium	Low	Very low
Questions										
Your satisfaction with the freedom of the media and television	30.9%	14.4%	27.8%	38.9%	10%	4.3%	4.3%	21.7%	39.1%	30.9%
Media (TVs) need to be managed	56.6%	2.3%	19.3%	31.8%	43.2%		8.7%	17.4%	17.4%	56.6%
Support and strengthen the growth of The ministry of information and culture of the afghanistanoftelevisions and their various programs	4.3%	25%	25%	7.1%	4.8%	52.2%	17.4%	21.7%	4.3%	4.3%
How do you assess the supervision of the Ministry of Intelligence?	4.8%	22.4%	35.8%	11.8%	3.5%	28.6%	23.8%	38.1%	4.8%	4.8%
The Commission for Violation of Mass Media has received complaints		19%	31%	10.7%	24%	25%	40%	25%	10%	
Your assessment of the extent to which the Media Violation Commission has received complaints from television stations		20%	47.7%	11.4%	1.1%	19%	28.9%	38.1%	14.3%	

The results show that among the respondents of the responsible managers of televisions, for the great achievements of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of free televisions, 18 people, who constituted 78.3% of the members of this sample, said that the Ministry Information and culture did not have any strong managerial points in the management of the country's free televisions. Eleven, who made up 47.8% of the sample, considered the media law to be one of the great achievements of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in managing free television. 23 people, who constituted

100% of the members of this sample, mentioned the freedom of the media and the provision of a good platform for information and entertainment without restrictions and censorship as the strong points of the ministry in the management of free television and 18 people, 78.3 % Of the members made this sample, the issuance of licenses and review of broadcasting policies and announcements of TV stations before broadcasting are among the strengths of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's free televisions.

In addition, out of the total number of respondents in charge of television, for the great weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of free television, 11, of which 47.8% of the respondents made up this sample, lacked a clear strategy and policy to He described the management of free television as one of the ministry's major managerial weaknesses. 16 people, who made up 69.8% of the sample, responded to the lack of strong, professional, responsible and adequate human resources as one of the ministry's weaknesses in managing free television. 5 people, who made up 21.7% of the members of this sample, lack of specific regulations, bills, regulations and ethical fertilizers for free television; 12 people, who made up 52.2% of the respondents; the lack of rule of law; 9 people, who made up 39.1% of the sample; lack of coordination and cooperation between the Ministry of Information, Culture and Media; 5 people, who constituted 21.7% of this sample, had the Ministry's tasteful and duplicitous attitude towards televisions, and 6 people, who constituted 26.1% of the members in charge of television, lacked the support and cooperation of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan. The great managerial weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan were expressed in the management of free television.

Our findings show that among the respondents, the members of the unions responded to the great achievements of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of free television, 65 people, which constituted 72.2% of the respondents in this sample, which the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan does not have any strong management points in the management of the country's free televisions. Eighteen, who made up 20% of the sample, cited the media law as one of the ministry's strong management points. 48 people, who accounted for 53.3% of the sample; freedom of expression and free television activities without censorship and restrictions; 29 persons, who constituted 32.2% of the respondents of this sample, issued licenses and review of broadcasting policies and announcements of televisions before broadcasting, and 19 persons, who constituted 21.1% of the respondents of the sample population of the unions, activity of the union. Journalists' unions have been mentioned as one of the prominent and strong points of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's free televisions.

In addition, among the respondents, members of the unions, for the great weaknesses of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan in the management of free television, 36, who made up 40% of the members of this sample, lacked the rule of law; 30 people, who made up 33.3% of the respondents, lacked a regular and legal media and television monitoring commission; 27 people, who made up 30.7% of the sample, the ministry's taste and duplicity; 23, which accounted for 25.6% of respondents; lack of regular strategy and policy for free television; 9 people, who made up 10% of the sample, the inability of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan to support and cooperate with their televisions and journalists; 24, of which 26.7% of respondents made up the sample; corruption; 28 people, who accounted for 31.1% of this sample, lacked strong, specialized and responsible human resources; 6, who made up 6.7% of the sample, lacked coordination between the ministry and

the televisions; Have pointed out the major managerial weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of free television.

Table 6: Intervention of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan from the perspective of responsible managers

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Confidence	Yes	21	91.3	91.3	91.3
	No	2	8.7	8.7	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 6, among the respondents of the responsible managers of free televisions for the intervention and management of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, 21 people, who constituted 91.3% of the sample members of the responsible managers, chose the answer yes and 2 Ton, who made up 8.7% of the members of this sample, chose the answer I do not know. From the findings, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of the responsible managers have thought that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan should intervene for the proper management of free television in case of publications that are against the law and media and cultural and religious values.

Table 7: The reason for non-intervention of the Ministry, from the perspective of responsible managers

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Confidence	Lack of management, transparency and proper accountability in the ministry	2	8.7	8.7	8.7
	Lack of ability, accountability and rule of law by this ministry	13	56.5	56.5	65.2
	Fear that freedom of expression will not be questioned and tyranny will not be exercised	4	17.4	17.4	82.6
	No	4	17.4	17.4	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 7, among the respondents of responsible managers, for non-intervention of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, 2 people, who constituted 8.7% of the sample of responsible managers of televisions, lack of management, transparency and accountability. They were chosen right in the ministry. Thirteen, who accounted for 56.5% of the sample of responsible managers, chose the answer of lack of ability, accountability and the rule of law. 4, who constituted 17.4% of the members of this sample, chose the answer of fear that the principle of freedom of expression would not be questioned and tyranny would not be exercised, and 4, who constituted 17.4% of the members of this sample, answered no I was chosen to know. From the results obtained, it can be inferred that most of the respondents of the responsible managers expressed the reason for non-intervention of The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan as the lack of ability, recourse and rule of law by this ministry.

Table 8: The reason for the lack of proper management of televisions by The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan from the perspective of responsible managers

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Total percentage
Co	Most TV stations are backed by certain groups, which the Ministry of Power does not have the power to fight	11	47.8	47.8	47.8

The scope of The Ministry Of Information And Culture Of The Afghanistan's authority to control the media is not clear in the media law	4	17.4	17.4	65.2
The ministry itself is corrupt and the cause of administrative corruption	3	13.0	13.0	78.3
No	5	21.7	21.7	100.0
Total	23	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 8, among the respondents of the responsible TV executives for non-opposition and management, 11 (47.8% of the participants in this survey), the answer of most TV stations is supported by certain groups, which the ministry did not have the power to fight them, they chose. 4 people, who constituted 17.4% of the respondents in this sample, do not know the answer within the competence of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in controlling the media in the media law, 3 people, who constituted 13% of the members of this sample, the answer of the Ministry itself is corrupt and the cause of corruption was chosen and 5 people, who constituted 21.7% of this sample, had no opinion on this question. The findings can be interpreted as saying that most of the respondents of the responsible managers of the televisions stated that the main reason for the mismanagement of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan was the support of free televisions by special groups and the inability of the ministry to stand against them.

Qualitative findings

The results obtained from interviews with 6 media experts on the strengths and weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's free televisions show that, according to experts, The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in recent years more management methods from above It has taken the ruling and the condemned down and has not paid much attention to the proper management of the media, especially free television. For the past 10 years, the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has not offered appropriate management strategies for free media and their management that can lead the media to national interests and bring media coverage to the attention of Afghan society, and today television is rampant. They continue to publish.

Experts also believed that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan had made good strides in the management of free television over the past few years, which could not be ignored, including media freedom, uncensored free television activity, licensing, and review. Letters (licenses) according to the legal system of punishing the media, amending the media law of 1346 and approving the media law of 1384 and 1388, the establishment of media unions, holding several seminars on freedom of expression and the media and the ministry's advice on free media has been cited as one of the strong points of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan in managing free media, especially free television. On the other hand, these experts believe that the managerial weaknesses of this ministry are more prominent than its strengths, which cannot be ignored. they listed these weaknesses as follows:

First, breaking law by the ministry itself: According to the public media law, the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan has two responsibilities in managing free media. A: Establishment of the supreme media council, according to article 41 of the media law, under the umbrella of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, whose main purpose is to establish a regular and long-term policy for the better functioning of the mass media. B: Establishment of the public media commission based on article 42 of the media law, in which

9 members of this commission are highly educated professionals with experience in journalism and neutral with a view to ethnic and gender composition. According to media experts, according to Article 43 of the law on public media, it can be said that the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan acted contrary to the law on public media, and the supreme media council and its members were formed by the leadership of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan. It is said that the lack of a regular policy for the mass media in the last four years is the result of their work. On the other hand, instead of establishing a commission for mass media, the ministry has established a commission called the commission for investigating media violations, which was mentioned in the public media law of 2005, which said that the commission was set up illegally and whose members were appointed on the basis of personal relations, is undoubtedly weak in handling complaints and investigating violations of the free media, and shows negligence in the performance of its duties and responsibilities.

Second, lack of rule of law: Experts believed that there was a lack of strong will on the part of the Afghan government, especially the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, a lack of professional journalists in the Afghan media, countries interfering in the Afghan media, and the media not relying on their own feet. Factors involved in the lack of media management have prevented the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan from enforcing the law on media outlets operating in violation of the mass media law. However, this ministry has enforced the law in cases where the law rules in its favour and has the power to enforce the law, and has adopted indifference in and many other matters in the implementation of the law. On the other hand, he did not ignore the fact that when a responsible institution such as The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan does not obey the law, such as (forming a commission to violate the illegal media), no doubt the free media has taken over the law. The application of the law shows negligence and this in itself causes the law not to be applied.

Third, lack of regular long-term strategy and policy: According to article 42 of the public media law, the supreme media council, which operates under the umbrella of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, is obliged to provide a clear and orderly policy for free media in accordance with the principles of libertarianism. The cultural values of the country should be designed and codified, but the Supreme Media Council has been weak in designing and compiling such a policy so far and has not proposed any policy since the enactment of the public media law in 2009, and if it has, it is still available to the media. Not located free.

Fourth, weak leadership: From the beginning of the interim government until today, The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan has always been led by weak and inefficient leaders, who focused more on the old management of the 1940s and 1950s and were unaware of the new media management according to today's liberal principles and system. Some of these leaders opposed the freedom of expression, and secretly tried to prevent the growth of freedom of expression and the media, while others, with Western democratic ideas, allowed the media to freely and irresponsibly publish freely. have given. The weak leadership of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has led to indifference and indifference in the control and supervision of free media and the inability to manage the media properly.

Fifth, the Ministry's taste in dealing with the media: Experts believe that one of the other managerial weaknesses of The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan is the Ministry's dual and tasteful treatment of the media, which are affiliated with and supported by a particular group or country. Despite repeated violations, they have never been demanded or criticized by the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, but the media, which did

not have great party and group support, are always criticized and questioned, even their cases without careful investigation. It is sent to the prosecutor's office as required by law.

Sixth, inability to protect televisions and journalists' rights: Media experts believed that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has done little to institutionalize freedom of expression and has shown the least support for television and its journalists. According to article 2 of the mass media law, one of the goals of the mass media law is to develop and protect freedom of expression and journalism. Implementing the mass media law is one of the priorities of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan. Freelancers and journalists' rights have shown the least support and cooperation. In addition, the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has acted weakly and inefficiently in protecting and guaranteeing the right to freedom of thought and expression as a responsible and accountable institution.

Seventh, inability to exercise its powers: If the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan passes the media law, there is transparency in media funding, red lines of national interests are defined, the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan can monitor media actions, because the law has drawn a clear line through the media, The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan.

Also, the results obtained from interviews with two officials of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan about the strengths and weaknesses of the ministry in the management of free television show as follows:

According to ministry officials, The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan has taken over vertical management from top to bottom because according to the principle of hierarchy, public administration in Afghanistan is governed by the same procedure in all government institutions. Free television can be broadcast freely, but in cases where national interests, culture and morals, personalities are harmed, the ministry never allows free television to impersonate and create chaos, but in a country like Afghanistan in any field. The hands behind the back are hiding, it is difficult or impossible to manage free TVs. Therefore, it can be said that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has not adopted an indifferent management method, but a conservative management method. Because 1) The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan believes in the growth of the media and the strengthening of freedom of expression, and because freedom of expression is not questioned and tyranny is not exercised, it has adopted this method. 2) External interference has caused this ministry to remain silent in the management of free televisions, under this ministry it has no ability to fight and intervene.

In addition, officials acknowledged that the ministry of intelligence had not been able to form a public media commission since the passage of the Public Media Law, but that the commission was being set up as required by the public media law. they added that the members of the commission were not appointed by the leadership of the ministry based on tastes and relations, but all members of both commissions were appointed by experts, civil society, the Journalists' Union, the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, the faculty of journalism ... public commissions are appointed, and their members are mostly experts and experienced in the field.

According to the officials of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, the main factors that the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan cannot manage free televisions are any external interventions in controlling and supervising free televisions, lack of strong and large support, lack of sufficient financial resources to establish a supervisory and

control management. The representative of free media has mentioned the existence of administrative corruption during the appointment and dismissal of senior managers of this ministry, and these factors have caused a challenge in the management of free media in the country for the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan. True free TVs show their shortcomings.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study of the strengths and weaknesses of the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan in the management of the country's free televisions, the following conclusions can be appealed: The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan has mostly adopted a top-down management method or vertical management. The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has been able to perform very well in the activities of free televisions, licensing and reviewing the broadcasting policies of televisions before their broadcasting. Also, it has done very poorly in managing the country's free television. Pursuant to the law on public media, the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan has designated it to control free television and to refrain from using legal means; However, the establishment of an illegal commission under the name of the commission for violation of mass media did not follow, and the ministry's disregard for the law has caused free televisions to show indifference in following the law. Also, the ministry of information and media culture correctly it cannot manage, but there are several main reasons why the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan does not manage free television properly, and these factors are: weak and indifferent leadership or conservative; freest televisions are supported and strengthened by domestic and foreign groups, especially foreign parties and intelligence. The management principles of the libertarian system are not fully aware; they do not manage the media under the same pretext. Corruption and lack of accountability and transparency in the management of this ministry, the ministry of intelligence, like other government institutions, has become corrupt, and this administrative corruption has caused the good management and governance of this ministry to be constantly criticized by the media, and this administrative corruption has caused it. The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan does not have the financial capacity to establish an independent and separate management to control and monitor the media.

Recommendations

In order to control and monitor well free media, especially free television, in accordance with the principles of free media control system, the following solution is proposed: Changing the liberal system of the media to a liberal system with social responsibility. The ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, as a responsible and competent institution, must act seriously in following and enforcing the law on mass media. Establish a regular public media commission with the task of monitoring, investigating violations and handling media complaints, as required by the media law, and perform their duties and commitments in accordance with the media law. The supreme media council, as required by law, must formulate a policy for the mass media so that the media can know and understand the scope of its activities and publications. The inefficient leaders and managers have prevented the ministry from properly managing free media. The authority supporting and strengthening the media must be specified before issuing a license for the ministry of information and culture of Afghanistan, so that after issuing a license, The ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan does not use pressure on its own authority and does not publish in accordance with its reference goals. Develop a specific law to protect the rights of journalists. More funding should be made available to the ministry of information and culture of the Afghanistan to establish a management that oversees and controls the free media. The members of all commissions,

especially the public media commission, should be composed of members of the ministry, Supreme Court, civil society, journalists' unions, parliament and experienced experts to monitor the free media in a committed, honest and impartial manner and to monitor media violations. Investigate and properly investigate the media complaints of journalists and the media.

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